

Customer Satisfaction in Banking Service

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Abstract

Customer satisfaction is the main objective of any banking sector to provide quality product which help in retaining the customer. In Traditional banking the customers used to stand in a long queue to fill the forms for deposit or withdrawals but now the modern banking does not face all this difficulty it has bought modern technology to provide better satisfaction to its customers like online banking, credit card facilities, online payment and transaction. This study is to understand if the customers are satisfied with the modern technology and does the bank put an effort to educate their customer regarding upcoming technology which the bank is going to adopt. Banking being a customer-oriented service industry, customer satisfaction is the KING of criteria to assess any banking business.

Keywords: services, customer satisfaction, modern banking technology, customer oriented service, customer-retention.

Introduction

The Service Sector in India contributes 53% of Indian GDP even though it is not a dominant sector in the country; it significantly attracts the foreign investments. And also contributes to the significant exports and employment at large scale opportunity is provided by the Service Sector. A wide variety of activities are covered under service sector in India such as transport, hotel and restaurants, trade, communication and storage, real estates, community, business services, insurance and financing. One of the important key drivers in Indian economy is the Service Sector, the estimated cost contributed by the service sector is about 54.0 per cent in 2017-18 of India's gross value added and among total population about 28.6 per cent have employed. The net services exports India increased year on year to US\$ 77,562.89 million in 2017-18 from 14.98 per cent.

Banking Sector

In India the banking service consist of public sector banks are about 27, private sector banks are 21, foreign banks are 49, RRB are 56, urban banks are 1,562 and rural banks are 94,384.

The Indian banks are mainly focusing on risk management by embracing the international banking system, so that the accessibility is made easy to the customers which automatically leads to a satisfied customer and a loyal customer to the bank.

Literature Review

Vyas, V., & Raitani, S. (2014) the research says that many customers are switching their banks which provides better services. The research has found nine factors which are critical that subsidize in switching the banks. One of the most interesting motorists of all the drivers is customer satisfaction which is the main reason for substituting behaviour of the customers. Banks must come out with better approach that increases the customer satisfaction.

Machogu, A. M., & Okiko, L. (2015) research brought to light that with e-banking complexities on customer satisfaction. Results shows that there are factors which leads to customer satisfaction particularly in e-banking, which is one of the very important and fast-growing way of doing banking. Factors are accessibility, convenience, security, privacy, content, design, speed, fees and charges have influence on customer satisfaction where the other factors notified have no significant influence

Ameme, B., & Wireko, J. (2016) claimed in his research that in today's competitive world where technology plays a very important role and if we talk about banking sector or industry there is a positive relationship between technology and customer satisfaction. They also found that if the bank wants to become the market leader in the competitive environment it must use the innovation approach in all the aspects like products and services.

Kaur, N., & Kiran, R. (2015) founded in their research which was on public, private and foreign shows that customer are more satisfied with the services quality of the foreign banks then the private and public banks

Research Gap

Above listed all review literature gives insight for services offered by banking sectors and customer satisfaction and benefits offered by the banks with various findings. The gap has been found in many areas especially in data analysis and research methodology that has been adopted and whether the customers are aware of the benefits offered to them by the banks, do banks educate their customers about modern banking

Statement of Problem

Are the customers open to the technology savvy banking system?

Before privatisation, the banking sectors was not given more importance the people were not aware of the importance of banking sector and the banking sectors did not provide satisfying services to its customers later when the banks were privatised advanced technology was adopted and new schemes to attract the customers but most of the customers are not aware of the technology and benefits offered to them.

Objective

The main objective of the study is to know whether the customers are aware of the technology which the bank incorporates and are they educated on it. Keeping this as a base three objective is framed.

- To determine whether customers are satisfied with the services offered by the banks.
- To examine if customers are aware of the technology and modern trends in banking service.
- To understand if banking sector educates about the technology to its customers.

Scope of the study

The study was to understand if the customers are satisfied with the service provided and whether they are aware of the technology that is been incorporated by the banks and the research targets certain age groups to know whether they utilize the benefits offered.

Limitation

The study “Customer Satisfaction in Banking System: Are the Customers Open to Technology Savvy in Banking System.

- This study is basically limits the sample size.
- The study is covered only to certain age groups restricted only to Bangalore city.

Research Methodology

Research methodology used in the research is online survey, the survey is conducted through well-structured questioners, self-administered format and the reference is taken from journals, various articles and some research papers.

Data Analysis

1. How frequently do you perform online transaction?

Chart 1

Source: Excel Output

Inference

From the above chart 1, 41.5% of customers perform online transaction whenever required, 24.6% use once in a week, 10.8% do not perform any online transaction. By this it is notified that customers perform online transactions as per their convenience as and when it is required.

2. Are you aware of the following banking services?

Chart 2

Source: Excel Output

Inference

From the above chart-2 it is predicted that majority of the customers are aware of plastic cards i.e., debit card and credit card and they also prefer using more off ATM and cash deposit machines, NEFT and RTGS, kiosk are not frequently used by the customers.

3. How satisfied are you with the banking service?

Chart 3

Source: Excel Output

Inference

From the above chart-3 it is depicted that the majority of the customers do prefer using banking services either it could be traditional or modern method of banking. As the specific data is analysed through ranking that is 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest.

Findings

- Proper guidelines are not provided to the customers regarding the usage of technology.
- Privacy is the major issue in the modern banking system.
- Even though there are flaws in modern banking system majority of the customers prefer modern banking as a means of transaction.
- The satisfaction level of the customers is improving drastically certain changes in the system will lead to greater happy customers.
- Customers are not given the opportunity to tell about their grievances.

Recommendations

- Customer satisfaction should be driving force of the banking sector.
- The bank has to spread awareness about the upcoming changes in the technology.
- The network and services has to be improved.
- Customers should be given the opportunity to put forth their problems and immediate solution to be made available.

Conclusion

In today's scenario there is a massive development in the banking sector, one of the main reasons being the growth of latest technology. Indian banking industry at the present time has witnessed the roll out of innovative payment transaction and deposits. These banks concentrate more on customer perspective and adopt the latest technology to reduce the work load. Certain examples are ATM machines; cash deposit machine, Net banking and mobile banking etc.

Earlier traditional bank was the only way for making any transactions and it was basically public sector wherein government played a major role by taking into the consideration of profit and social obligations. At present there are several private sectors banks which are established throughout the nation these private sectors are not owned by the government and they are mainly into profit consideration.

From the study it is found that certain changes in the functioning of the system will have a great impact on the customer's satisfaction. Before any kind of technology is adopted the customers have to be well informed and educated about it. Customer's satisfaction should be the end goal of any banking sector.

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